

Sedimentological and petrographical attributes of a mixed siliciclastic-shoal carbonate, embayment system: A coupled approach on rocks of mid-Jurassic (Callovian-Oxfordian) Chari Formation, Kutch Basin, Western India.

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Abstract

The Chari Formation exposed at Ler Dome is studied to establish sedimentary environments based primarily on petrography supplemented with lithofacies distribution of mixed siliciclastic-carbonate rocks deposited within Callovian-Oxfordian intervals. The dome is extensively studied for paleontological research, but a petrography-based analysis to establish the sedimentary architecture of the siliciclastic-carbonate rocks is a progressive approach for its characterization. The Chari Formation represents a diversified lithofacies constitution, based on lateral and vertical variations of lithologies, ten different lithofacies are identified: Mud-flake conglomerate; Low-angle cross-stratified sandstone; Carbonaceous grey shale; Fossiliferous sandstone (shelly beds); Concreted shales; Ferruginous sandstone; Concreted mudstone; Sandy Limestone; Oolitic limestone; Dhosa Oolite. Based on petrographic studies, petrofacies are classified as: Sandstone petrofacies; Ferruginous Mudstone petrofacies; Shale petrofacies and Mud flake conglomerate petrofacies. Microfacies analysis of the carbonates are classified into: Sandy micrite and Sandy Bio-micrite microfacies; Oo-micrite microfacies and Dhosa Oolite microfacies. The petrofacies and microfacies were divided in six facies associations, grouped into three facies belts: Lagoon-subtidal bar complex to Shoal environment and later to an Open marine, winnowed platform environment, facing the sea from the coast. The presence of a retrogradation stacking pattern in the overall sequence, indicates a Transgressive Systems Tract (TST), separated by periodic Transgression-Regression cycles characterized by burrowed concretions and reworked concretions within the middle part of the succession. The Dhosa Oolite Member occurring at the top of the succession represents the maximum flooding surface (MFS). Previously, it was discussed by various authors that sediments in the basin exhibits storm dominated shallow marine shelf cyclic sedimentation under frequently changing condition of sea level. With the help of the detailed petrographic and lithological studies, a conceptual depositional model is proposed with insights to sequence stratigraphic framework, entailing that the rocks of the Chari Formation were formed in a transgressive, mixed siliciclastic-shoal carbonate, embayment system.